

Issue with Fisher Information and the Correspondence Principle?

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. May 22, 2019

The classical Fisher information, F , in one dimension is given in the literature as: $\int dx d(x) [d/dx \ln(d(x))]^2$ ((1)) where $d(x)$ is the spatial probability density. For quantum mechanics, (1) uses $d(x)=W^*(x)W(x)$ for quantum mechanics, where $W(x)$ is the complex wavefunction. The Cramer Rao inequality is used to show how $1/F$ is related to the variance of $d(x)$. For a bound state wavefunction, which is real, one may show Fisher's information leads to $\int dx v(x)v(x) d(x)$ which is proportional to the average kinetic energy. Using the correspondence principle, $d(x)$, for high energy levels, should approach $C/v(x)$ where $v(x)$ is the classical velocity. On the other hand, using the definition of F directly with $d(x)=C/v(x)$ leads to a different result. This seems unusual. We try to investigate in this note to see that quantum features exist even in the high energy limit. The Fisher information calculated with $W(x)W(x)=C/v(x)$ seems to capture quantum information, while that with $d(x)=C/v(x)$, information about the envelope function.

Probability Density in Quantum Mechanics

Bound state quantum mechanics seems to use conditional complex probability $P(p/x) = \int dp \exp(ipx) / W(x)$, where $W(x)$ is the wavefunction $W(x) = \int dp \exp(ipx)$. One may argue that at point x , the kinetic energy, averaged over all p from minus infinity to infinity equals classical kinetic energy:

$$[\text{Sum over } p \text{ } p^2/2m \int dp \exp(ipx)] / W(x) = (-1/2m) [d/dx d/dx W(x)]/W(x) = .5 m v(x)v(x) \quad ((2))$$

Here $v(x)$ is the classical velocity given by $.5m v(x)v(x) + V(x) = E_n$ where E_n is the quantum energy of the n th level. Thus, bound state quantum mechanics is linked to classical physics for every energy level, not just high ones. Furthermore, the wavefunction is often periodic (e.g. the quantum oscillator), so the density $W(x)W(x)$ has many humps. Even though the density has an envelope related to the classical probability density $C/v(x)$, the humps still satisfy ((1)) at each point x . Thus, in terms of derivatives of $W(x)$, even at high energy levels where $W(x)W(x)$ may be approximated by $C/v(x)$, a function of $d/dx W(x)$ or $d/dx d/dx W(x)$ cannot, it seems, be replaced by an expression using $W(x)=\text{sqrt}(C/v(x))$ because this does not satisfy ((2)).

A problem occurs when one begins with a function containing a spatial derivative of $W(x)$, such as Fisher information, and is able to write it in terms of a function containing no derivatives of $W(x)$. For example:

$$\int dx d/dx [W(x)d/dx W(x)] = \int dx [d/dx W(x)] [d/dx W(x)] + \int dx W(x) d/dx d/dx W(x) \quad ((3))$$

The integral on the left hand side is zero because $[W(x)d/dx W(x)]$ should vanish at plus and minus infinity very rapidly. Then:

$$\text{Fisher Information} = 2m \int dx \frac{1}{2m} v(x)v(x) W(x)W(x) \quad ((4))$$

Thus, Fisher information is proportional to the average kinetic energy in the quantum system. Given that ((4)) contains density= $W(x)W(x)$, one may replace this with $C/v(x)$ for high energy levels according to the correspondence principle. [In a somewhat related manner in (2), the authors calculate quantum Shannon's energy:

$-\int dx W(x)W(x) \ln[W(x)W(x)]$ for the quantum oscillator for high n using exactly this approach. This gives them the dependence of the Shannon's entropy of a Hermite polynomial as a function of n for n approaching infinity. The result matches a value obtained without making use of the correspondence principle.]

The issue is that ((4)) which is Fisher's information for the quantum case does not equal the value obtained by using the definition ((1)) with $d(x)=C/v(x)$. This seems to be due to the fact that $d/dx W(x)$ is not the same as $d/dx \sqrt{C/v(x)}$. This, in turn, is due to the fact that $W(x)$ is periodic with a small period for large n (in many cases). Thus, even though peak points, which are close by match $C/v(x)$, the derivative of $W(x)$ makes use of even closer points which drop very rapidly and give a completely different derivative. If one used ((4)) naively, one would expect the result to be the same as that calculated for the classical case. After all, at first glance it might seem that both are used as bounds for the variance of $d(x)=W(x)W(x)$ which has an envelope $C/v(x)$. The variance, it seems, should only depend on the envelope. The oscillations should not change things much. Perhaps this suggests that the quantum Fisher's information represents something else.

Even though the classical envelope $C/v(x)$ may fit the quantum picture for high energy levels, quantum mechanics, as long as one is not dealing with derivatives of $W(x)$, it is in fact very different from classical physics, even at high n . This seems to contradict the correspondence principle which, if taken naively, may suggest classical physics is the limit of quantum mechanics. The classical Fisher expression seems to show that even if one has an expression in terms of $W(x)W(x)$ such as ((4)), its meaning in quantum mechanics and classical mechanics may be completely different, even for high energy levels.

Derivation of the Cramer Rao Inequality

In (3), a one dimensional derivation of the Cramer Rao inequality is presented. We briefly examine this derivation to see if it distinguishes between classical and quantum densities in any way. The derivation seem to rest on the Cauchy-Schwarz inequality:

$$\sqrt{\text{Var}(x) \text{Var}(B(x))} \geq |\text{cov}(x, B(x))| \quad ((5))$$

With $B(x) = \frac{d}{dx} \ln(d(x))$ | where $d(x) =$ probability density. For the classical case it is $C/v(x)$ classical and for the quantum $W(x)W(x)$. Note: $\text{Var}(B(x)) =$ Expectation of $[B(x)] = \int dx d(x) B(x)B(x)$ i.e. Fisher's information because $\int dx B(x) d(x)$ can be shown to be 0. Thus, the covariance must be found. For the quantum case, one has:

$$\text{cov}(x, B(x)) = \int dx W(x)W(x) x \frac{d}{dx} [W(x)W(x)]$$

[It is interesting to note that $\text{cov}(x, B(x))$ is proportional to a term in the entropy of a quasiparticle as described in (4). In that note, we use as probability a term $W(x)$ for $\exp(ipx)$ in Shannon's entropy expression $-\text{Probability} \ln[\text{Probability}]$. The $\exp(ipx)$ term leads to an entropy term proportional to $\text{cov}(x, B(x))$.]

The covariance may be written as:

$$\int dx \frac{d}{dx} [x W(x)W(x)] = \int dx W(x)W(x) + \int dx x \frac{d}{dx} [W(x)W(x)]$$

The integral on the LHS is 0 because for a bound state $W(x)$ goes to zero at plus and minus infinity. The first integral on the RHS is 1 because density is normalized. Thus, $|\text{cov}(x, B(x))| = 1$.

For the classical case, a similar argument seems to hold if $|v(x)|$ is the same at each endpoint. This should cover the case of an oscillator and a particle in a box with infinite potential walls.

$$\int dx \frac{d}{dx} [x C/v(x)] = \int dx C/v(x) + \int dx x \frac{d}{dx} [C/v(x)]$$

The integral on the LHS is zero if one puts the origin at $x=0$. The first integral on the right is 1 due to normalization, thus $|\text{cov}(x, B(x))| = 1$.

Thus, it seems the derivation of the Cramer Rao inequality sheds no light on differences between quantum mechanics and classical mechanics, other than the fact that the $\frac{d}{dx} d(x)$ is different for the two. In quantum mechanics, $d(x)$, the density, often has humps leading to very different derivative values than the that of $C/v(x)$, the envelope function. Both approaches, although leading to different results, seem to satisfy the Cramer Rao identity. This begs the question: For high energy levels, which approach is better? One would think that for quantum mechanics, one should use the quantum result proportional to $\int dx d(x) \cdot 5mv(x)v(x)$, i.e. the average kinetic energy. In such a case, one really does not have quantum mechanics becoming classical mechanics in the large energy level limit. Perhaps the two approaches are related to different variances of x . The classical approach deals with the variance of the envelope function, while the quantum mechanical with the very narrow humps due to the high frequency of the wavefunction in various cases.

Examples

Let consider briefly two examples to demonstrate the difference between the quantum and classical cases. First, consider a particle in a one dimensional box with an infinite potential at the walls. The wavefunction with $x_{center}=0$ is proportional to $\sin(kx-b)$ where k is the root mean square momentum. For high energy, one has a sine wave with a very high frequency, yet the envelope function is a horizontal line. In the quantum case, Fisher's information becomes proportional to:

$\int dx \sin(kx-b)\sin(kx-b) [k \cos(kx-b)/ \sin(kx-b)]^2$ proportional to $\int dx k^2 \cos(kx-b) \cos(kx-b)$ which is of the form of the average kinetic energy $k^2 (-1/2m) \int dx \sin(kx-b)\sin(kx-b)$.

Given that one is integrating over a cycle or half cycle, a cos squared or sine squared give the same result. The variance of x is $1/$ Fisher's information so one has $1/k^2$. As k^2 becomes very large, this variance becomes very small.

For the classical case, density is a horizontal line, so $d/dx d(x)=0$ and Fisher's information is 0. This shows the variance of x does not really make sense because each x is as good as the other. For a finite region, there would be a variance, but it would be dictated by the length of the region. In the quantum case, substituting the envelope of $d(x)=constant$ for $\cos(kx-b)\cos(kx-b)$ gives a finite result.

Next, consider the quantum oscillator. Fisher's information is $(2m) \int dx .5 mv(x)v(x) d(x)$. Thus, it is $(2m)$ Average kinetic energy, or half the energy, for all energy levels.

$$\text{Fisher's info quantum oscillator} = .5 [.5\hbar w (n+.5)] \quad ((6))$$

From the Cramer-Rao relationship:

$$\text{Var}(x) \geq 1/ \text{Fisher's info} = 2/En$$

Thus, the larger En , the lower the bound on $\text{Var}(x)$. This seems to pick up the small wavelength, high frequency of the humps of the high energy density. In other words, it seems one is obtaining quantum information.

For a classical oscillator, one may write $x= \sqrt{2E/k} \cos(\omega t)$ where $\omega=\sqrt{k/m}$, so a larger E corresponds to a larger amplitude.

$$\text{Fisher info classical oscillator} = \int dx C/ v(x)^5 k^2 x^2 \quad ((7))$$

because $m v(x) d/dx v(x)= -kx$. $C= \text{number } A/\sqrt{E}$ where A is the amplitude. If one uses $v(x) = \omega \sqrt{2E/k} \sin(\omega t)$ and $x=\sqrt{2E/k} \cos(\omega t)$, then ((7)) is of the form:

$$\text{constant} \int d(\omega t) \cos(\omega t)^2 / \sin(\omega t)^4 \quad ((8))$$

Where $A/\sqrt{E} = (kA)^2 / (Aw)^5 = k^*k C \sqrt{(k/2E)^2 w^4} = k^{(.3/4)} m^{(1/4)} / 4 (n+.5)^{(3/2)}$

if one uses $E = \hbar w (n+.5)$ and $A = \sqrt{2E/w}$. Thus, for high energies, the classical Fisher information becomes smaller, which means the variance of x increases because the amplitude of the oscillator increases.

Given that $\cos(wt)$ and $\sin(wt)$ both have even powers, integral tables give a solution for such an integral (5)

Integral $\sin^n(ax) \cos^m(ax) dx = -\sin^{(n-1)}(ax) \cos^{(m+1)} ax / a(m+n) + (n-1)/(m+n) \text{Integral } \sin^{(n-2)}(ax) \cos^m(ax) dx$
 $n \text{ not} = -m$

A similar result holds for reducing powers of $\cos(ax)$. It seems that $v(x)$ is zero at endpoints and so both results will reduce to:

Constant Integral $d(wt) = \text{constant } 6.28$ where the constant is a product of integers.

Conclusion

In conclusion, it seems using the definition of classical Fisher information ((1)) and applying $d(x) = W(x)W(x)$ for the quantum case and $d(x) = C/v(x)$ for the classical where $v(x)$ is the classical velocity from $.5mv(x)v(x) + V(x) = E$ yields different results, even though $W(x)W(x)$ has $C/v(x)$ as an envelope function for high energy levels according to the correspondence principle. Thus, one has to be careful when using the correspondence principle. Fisher's information for bound state quantum mechanics is an integral containing $W(x)W(x)$ and no derivatives in the average kinetic energy form. Thus, one would expect that for the high energy limit $W(x)W(x)$ could be replaced by $C/v(x)$. It can, but the meaning of the quantum Fisher's information differs from that of the classical one. There are two x variances in the quantum problem, that of the high frequency humps and that of the envelope function. The classical Fisher calculation only yields the latter. Thus, even for the high energy limit, quantum mechanics has features that differ greatly from those of classical physics. Furthermore, for any energy state, even the ground state, ((2)) holds showing that the second derivative with x of the wavefunction is proportional to classical kinetic energy. This second derivative is equivalent to an average of $p^*p/2m$ using $\exp(ipx)/W(x)$ as a complex probability.

References

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